

Quds Day and Public Ignorance of Historical Facts

Last Friday, the eleventh of Tir (July 2nd), was Quds Day, a day initiated by Ayatollah Ruhollah Khomeini, the founder of the Islamic Republic, and institutionalized in the Islamic world. On this day, millions of Muslims around the globe call for the liberation of Jerusalem, often unaware of the historical truths about the land of Israel.

Quds Day Rally in Rankooh

The truth is that the Arab-Israeli conflict is not about land; it is a religious war. Arabs have no shortage of land. They control about 22 countries with approximately 13.5 million square kilometers of territory, whereas Israel's area is only about 20,000 square kilometers, making it one of the smallest countries in the world.

The land of Israel belongs to the Jews, and this is historically defensible. Even the Quran and the Prophet of Islam acknowledged this. This is why, following the reproach of the Jews, the qibla (direction of prayer) was changed from Jerusalem to Mecca. By changing the qibla, the Prophet of Islam essentially delineated the boundaries between the Islamic world and Judaism. Had Muslims adhered to this delineation, the region and the world could have been at peace. Unfortunately, some have distorted historical facts, obstructing the path to peace.

For some, capturing Jerusalem equates to capturing the history of the prophets and dominating the cradle of monotheistic faiths. The Quran affirms the Jewish right to the land of Israel. For this reason, Morteza Motahhari attempted to depict Jews as a race distinct from the Israelites. He knew well that recognizing the roots of the Jewish people would undermine his ability to protest their return to their homeland. Consequently, he resorted to unfair tactics, questioning the Jewish roots.

For a Jew, Israel is sacred land entrusted to them by God, and Jerusalem is their qibla. Imagine if Mecca were conquered by Christians, who then ruled it for 1,000 years. Undoubtedly, Muslims, particularly Arabs, would declare jihad to reclaim Mecca, even if it took 10,000 years. This reality is evident to all today. Jews also have the right to defend their qibla passionately.

In Islamic jurisprudence, a non-Muslim is not allowed to enter Islamic holy places, let alone claim governance over them. Similarly, for a Jew who holds Jerusalem sacred, the city cannot be managed by Muslims. Arab Palestinians have the right to citizenship and residency in Israel, but due to Israel's religious identity, they cannot claim governance or leadership.

It is intriguing that even religious intellectuals, despite their knowledge of historical truths, continue to follow the venomous interpretation of Ruhollah Khomeini, which has caused global turmoil. It seems that this seed of hatred and falsehood has deeply taken root in some hearts.

It must be acknowledged that Quds Day contradicts the tradition of the Prophet of Islam, who 1,400 years ago closed the file of enmity between Arabs and Jews by changing the qibla. The Prophet left Jerusalem for the Jews and directed the Islamic world's attention to Mecca. Even in Shiite jurisprudence, the Mahdi (the twelfth Imam) will appear in Mecca with 313 companions, not in Jerusalem. He will not enter Jerusalem without the presence of Christ. This interpretation shows that even in Shiite jurisprudence, before Khomeini and figures like Yasser Arafat, the dominant view respected Jewish rights to Jerusalem.

For Christians, too, Jerusalem is the city of the promised kingdom and cannot be governed by Muslims, just as Mecca cannot be governed by non-Muslims.

It is illogical for the world to be engulfed in bloodshed over Israel's 20,700 square kilometers of land. The Arab world should be content with its 13.5 million square kilometers and recognize Israel's rights. The Islamic Republic should focus on its own oppressed people because, as the saying goes, "Charity begins at home." Certainly, the dream of conquering Jerusalem could become the Islamic Republic's worst nightmare. On the day the Revolutionary Guards approach Jerusalem, the Islamic Republic will fall. Therefore, the Islamic Republic should abandon its adventurism. Hamas' response to the events in Syria should serve as a great lesson for every Iranian.

Sources:

1. Surah Al-Ma'idah (5:23–24)
2. Tabari, History of Tabari, Beirut: Dar Al-Kutub Al-Islamiyyah, 1st Edition, Volume 2, p. 415; Ibn Athir, Al-Kamil, Beirut: Dar Sader, Volume 2, p. 115.
3. Surah Al-A'raf (7:137)
4. Surah Al-Isra (17)

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